

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable D1.2 PARC governance process timeline WP1

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¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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1. Authors and Acknowledgments

This report was prepared by the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES).

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2. Abbreviations

GB: Governing Board

GSB: Grant Signatory Board

MB: Management Board

ASR: Annual Summary Report

AWP: Annual Work Plan

PTFR: Periodic Technical and Financial Report

SRIA: Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda

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1. PARC governance process timeline

The reporting calendar for PARC was revised after the launch of the Partnership to better adapt it to the Commission's and PARC's needs. It now includes reporting periods of 18 months and one of 12 months near the end (instead of the initial reporting calendar with 4 periods of 20, 24, 24 and 16 months). Based on the provisions of the PARC Grant Agreement and according to the revised calendar fixed by the European Commission for the reporting periods and the submission of the Annual Work Plans and Annual Summary Reports, the following timeline for the physical and virtual meetings of the PARC consortium governance bodies has been built (see next page).

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2. Description of the process

The first Annual Work Plan (AWP) will cover a duration of 12 months (1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023). The first AWP budget will reflect the resources needed for the first year of activity as the AWP submitted with the proposal (meaning for the first 12 months of PARC). The second AWP will start on 1st May 2023 and will end on 30th April 2024.

Annual Summary Reports (ASR) were planned throughout the lifetime of the Partnership to provide feedback on the implementation of the activities. The first ASR will only be technical and will cover the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022 (8 months).

Further to the revision of the reporting calendar for PARC, ASRs will only be required the years when no periodic technical and financial report is due (i.e. there will be no need for an ASR end of 2023, 2026, 2027 and 2028), as the equivalent information will be provided in the relevant periodic reports due at the same time.

The first Periodic Technical and Financial Report (PTFR) will cover the first 18 months of PARC from 1 May 2022 to 31 October 2023 and will be due on 31 December 2023.

As a reminder, three boards are instrumental in preparing the PARC implementation documents, which include the AWP and Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA), and reporting on the progress and achievements (notably through the ASRs):

- The Management Board (MB): operational body that supports the Coordinator in the day-to-day implementation of the Grant Agreement based on the Description of Action and AWP.

- The Grant Signatory Board (GSB): manages the contractual implementation of PARC both on the scientific and administrative levels. It has an important role, in collaboration with the MB and Governing Board (GB), in the provision of input in the PARC orientations and priorities, and for the identification of synergies, resources and capacities between Participants. The GSB:

- Provides input to the PARC SRIA prior to its presentation to the Governing Board
- Approves the AWP and associated budget, and ASRs before submission to the HaDEA taking account of input and opinion of the GB and approval of the achievement of the most significant milestones;

- The Governing Board (GB): overarching body of PARC that provides the highest level strategic steering of the Partnership and brings in the political commitment for the uptake of PARC Results and its sustainability.

Two meetings per year are planned for the GB and GSB (one physical meeting and one virtual meeting) and other consultations, via online meetings or through other means, may also be implemented, as required. The physical meetings will be ideally organised back to back with MB meetings.

Governing Board meetings

- During the first year of PARC, the PARC Coordination Team plans to organise a meeting of the GB in November 2022 to provide input and opinions on the PARC AWP for the second year and the PARC ASR and discuss and provide suggestions for the strategy and priorities for year 3.
- For the next years:
 - Physical GB meetings will take place once a year in November. The objective will be to provide input and opinions on the PARC progression (AWPs, SRIA and ASR) before submission to the EC in December and discuss progress, indicators, sustainability, as well as the strategy for the next AWP that will be worked on by the MB and GSB over the spring/summer.
 - Virtual meetings of the GB will be organised in June/July each year to get inputs from the GB for the preparation of the future AWPs.
- Additional virtual GB meeting(s) and/or written consultation(s) (through forms, poll, and emails) may be organised on other specific topics if needed.

Grant Signatory Board meetings

- During the first year of PARC, a virtual GSB meeting will be organised in November/early December 2022, to approve the second AWP and associated budget and 1st ASR before submission to HaDEA
- For the next years, the PARC Coordination Team is considering to plan:
 - A physical meeting of the GSB in June each year in order to prepare the AWP of the next year and update the PARC Rolling SRIA.
 - Virtual meetings of the GSB in November/early December each year to discuss progress and approve the AWP for the next year and associated budget and annual summary report of the previous year before submission to HaDEA.
- Additional virtual GSB meeting(s) and/or written consultation(s) (through forms, poll, and emails) may be organised, if needed.

Management Board meetings

Monthly MB meetings will be organised all along the Partnership's lifetime, with two physical meetings per year, one meeting in June back-to back to the GSB meeting and one in November, back-to-back to the GB meeting. The other MB meetings will take place online. The exact dates of meetings for the whole year for each Consortium Body will be fixed at the beginning of each year.

Consortium meetings

Besides the kick-off and final meetings, two consortium meetings will be organised all along the Partnership's lifetime. The dates put on the scheme above are provisional ones. These meetings will offer good opportunities to share among the PARC members what has been achieved yet, what are the difficulties encountered and how to solve them, what still need to be done to comply with PARC objectives and what are the emerging topic PARC should address.

Other bodies such as the SF, IB, DEP B will also support the PARC consortium in achieving their objectives.